

The Level Of Academic And Professional Preparation Of Applied Education And Training Institute Graduates In Performing The Assigned Work In In Private And Public Sector From Their Perspective

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Abstract

The study aims at finding out the level of academic and professional preparation for graduates of faculties, and institutes of applied education and training to perform the work assigned to them in their in private and public sector from their perspective. The study sample consisted of (6345) workers in the government and private sectors. To achieve the goal of the study a questionnaire was developed according to the following dimensions, the employees' ability of self-development, the theoretical and practical courses, and general culture that has been studied in the faculties and institutes, the reason for choosing the specialization, their willingness to work, matching the specialization to the work they do, as well as economic and job satisfaction for graduates where their validity and reliability has been verified. The findings showed that the level of academic and professional preparation for graduates was average. The results revealed there are statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of an academic and professional preparation level for graduates of faculties in favour of females. Moreover, there are no statistically significant differences in the government and private sector where it was moderate as the other dimensions except for some practical courses in favour of the government sector. The outcomes unveiled the existence of significant statistical differences was moderate and on all dimensions in favour of the field of specialization.

Introduction

International challenges and strong competition urge employers to hire highly skilled graduates to flourish their businesses. Graduates need essential skills to be effective in their jobs such as communication skills, information technology, problem-solving, teamwork, and others. To enhance employment skills, there are a set of factors that must be taken into consideration, namely: the structure of the curriculum and effective application in teaching because it enables graduates to acquire skills that employers consider necessary. Students acquire two types of skills during their academic years: technical skills and non-technical skills. Technical skills refer to knowledge of scientific content, which is necessary to work in a specific field. However, non-technical skills, are skills that are necessary for all jobs or professions and are known as employment skills, including communication skills, problem-solving skills, decision-making skills, and the skill of dealing with others and teamwork. Higher education institutions are responsible for developing graduate skills necessary for employment by applying various teaching methodologies, enhancing student participation and involvement in a range of activities, especially societal ones (Hodgman, 2018).

To strengthen the relationship between employers and graduates, facilitating environment should be prepared in faculties and universities that provide graduates with such skills, which are required by the public and private sectors. Thus, it focuses on a set of components, including communication and interaction between students and the university faculty employees. This would exemplify the important fruitful interaction between the work environment and educational institutions. The need for community cooperation leads to research and creativity enhancement. Therefore, students should be fully aware of employers' expectations and the requirements of numerous skills. Besides, the combination of all the taught skills like the communication and interaction between students and university faculty employees, the training courses at the university the participation of employers in designing and providing courses contribute to achieving a very positive result for developing employment skills that qualify professional graduates to help change work environments. Moreover, basic skills include handling information skills, communication skills, and problem solving by making use of knowledge and creativity (Andrews & Higson, 2008).

Human development is one of the most important elements for the advancement and progress of civilized societies. From this point, the State of Kuwait has taken care of its students by providing free education. The

government concentrates on various educational institutions, starting from early childhood until the university level, higher and professional education stage required for the labor market. The wealth of society is not only measured by the amount of natural and material resources it has but also human and youth resources are added to it. Human resources are the basis of the renaissance and human civilizations throughout all ages. Therefore, in any society economic development does not succeed except through the investment of the human element, as it is the main factor and stimulates people's progress and prosperity. There is a direct relationship between the rates of economic growth of the society and the decrease in unemployment rates and the rise in the educational level (Al-Omro, 2020).

From this standpoint, human development is related to professional and higher education to accomplish integration and sustainable development in the social, economic, political, environmental and technological fields. The natural place to achieve human development is the knowledge and educational system. Therefore, the more the education quality is higher, the higher the human development level for political, economic, social and technological advancement and development (Helyer & Lee, 2014). There is no unified educational system that is suitable for all educational institutions due to the type of institution, the disciplines offered, its objectives, and the social conditions surrounding it (Tribus, 2009).

The Public Authority for Applied Education and Training is considered the largest educational institution in Kuwait ahead of Kuwait University, where ten thousand students graduate each year. According to the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training statistics, there were (9,356) graduates in 2015/2016, while Kuwait University has (6,490) graduates in the same year. The Public Authority Applied Education and Training was founded in December 1982, and its establishment law stipulated the purpose is to provide and develop the national workforce in a manner that ensures facing the deficiencies in the national technical workforce and meeting the country's development needs. The authority consists of the applied education and research sector and the training sector.)

The applied education and research sector provides five faculties for the student to enroll in after completing the secondary stage, namely Faculty of Basic Education, Faculty of Technological Studies, Faculty of Business Studies, Faculty of Health Sciences, and Faculty of Nursing. It is worth mentioning that the Faculty of Basic Education is the only one in which students study for 4 years to achieve a bachelor's degree in the field of special education or educational support services. As for the Faculty of Business Studies, the student studies for two years, after which he obtains a diploma in the field of administrative sciences, accounting, marketing, insurance, and banking.

The Faculty of Technological Studies differs in that the student studies there for two and a half years to have the diploma as an assistant engineer in various technological sciences. There is only one major in which the student obtains a baccalaureate in chemical technology engineering after studying for at least four years. As for the Faculty of Nursing, it offers a diploma in nursing after studying for two years while a Bachelor's degree after studying for four years. As for the Faculty of Health Sciences, it also offers a diploma in various health sciences such as pharmacy, health, preventive measures, medical laboratories, and oral and dental health after studying two years, whereas a Bachelor's degree in environmental sciences after studying four years.

The training sector includes nine institutes, namely the Institute of Communications and Navigation, the Industrial Training Institute in Sabah Al-Salem, the Industrial Training Institute in Shuwaikh, the Construction Institute, the Nursing Institute, the Vocational Training Institute, the Tourism and Beauty Institute, the Higher Institute for Administrative Services, the Higher Energy Institute and special training courses. Students enroll in these institutes after the intermediate and secondary stages, and the Institute of Communications and Navigation provides a diploma for high school graduates after studying for two years. The student becomes a technician, while after the intermediate stage the student gets the title of technical assistant in the disciplines of navigation, radio and external networks and central office. The Institute of Communications and Navigation provides a diploma after studying for two years for high school graduates, so that the student gets a technical title, while the student after the intermediate level gets the title of technical assistant in the specializations of navigation, radio, external networks, and central office.

The Industrial Training Institutes in Shuwaikh and Sabah Al-Salem graduate technicians from students according to the needs of the labour market after studying two years at the Shuwaikh Industrial Institute and three years at the Sabah Al-Salem Industrial Institute. While the Institute of Nursing grants the diploma in health and preventive services at hospitals and clinics through a three-year study after the ninth year of general education. The Vocational Training Institute offers a vocational qualification diploma for students after the intermediate stage and four years of study. The Construction Training Institute provides technicians in the construction sector after the intermediate stage students study for three years. The Higher Institute for Administrative Services provides theoretical knowledge and applied skills for secretarial work and its tasks to graduate after the intermediate stage and an academic year. The Higher Institute of Energy provides technicians

and assistant technicians after the secondary and intermediate level in operating Energy generators, water stations, and maintenance. Also, special courses offer their technical and specialized programs according to the needs of the Labour market in various sectors of the state.

1. Previous Studies

A work team from the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training prepared a similar study on (4435) graduates from 1996 until 2000. The representative sample of all the faculties and institutes of the authority was (26,894) students, equivalent to 16% of the total graduates during the mentioned period whereas the sample of the officials consisted of (604) administrators from different work authorities. The General Organization for Social Security and the Public Authority for Civil Information were contacted to determine the graduate work sites. The study revealed that (74.5%) of the total sample work in the government sector, while (15%) work in defense and security, (3.1%) work in the oil sector, (1.1%) work in the joint sector, (1.7) work in the private sector, and (0.3%) are retired where (4.3%) of them did not have data. The results of the study showed that job satisfaction is achieved by (79.68%), the fulfillment of choosing the desired major is (78.90%), the general competency of the graduate is (77.44%), and the percentage of how work is related to the specialization (75.13%), the graduates need for in-service training (69.2%). Besides, the findings revealed that the preparation programs are suitable for job requirements is (65.63%) and the willingness to work in the private sector (42.2%).

Kuwait University conducted a study in (2010) aimed at assessing the labor market and its trends through the reality of quantitative and qualitative appointments of Kuwait University outcomes and their analyses, determining the level of alignment of the university's outputs with the needs of the labor market. Furthermore, the study examined the time rate of appointments and their implications for determining the quantitative and qualitative requirements of the university's outputs and predicting the requirements of the Kuwaiti labor market and expected job opportunities. The results of the study revealed that there is a surplus in the expected graduation from faculties of arts, especially in the field of history and philosophy for the labor market.

The study recommended coordination between the labor market and higher education institutions, the exchange of experiences and information, and the establishment of joint mechanisms to achieve congruence between the outputs of education and the labor market, support for scientific and medical faculties, education, administrative sciences, and engineering following the needs required for the coming years. Moreover, legalize admission in some humanitarian specialties and work to develop these specialties by providing them with an assistant or double specialization, and adopting appropriate strategies to raise the efficiency of science curricula and develop them in line with the rapid changes. The study results should be applied when developing the admission policy at Kuwait University for the coming years and distributing students to serve the needs of the labor market.

Kuwait University (2013) elucidated in a study on the expected quantitative development of the baccalaureate graduates between the market needs and the outputs of Kuwait University for the years (2012-2016). The most important results were summarized in the existence of a surplus equivalent to double the amount or even more in the labor market than the needs of theoretical faculties at a percentage of (117%). On the contrary, the university's output covers only about half of the market's need for professional specializations by (51%) and the least in scientific faculties with (32%) of the actual labor market needs for the years (2012-2016).

Subagi Waladdin (2020) performed a study aimed at highlighting the effect of the outputs of the general training programs on developing the personal and technical skills of the trainee from the perspective of the trainees in Lebanon. The study sample consisted of (768) trainees from all the governorates of Lebanon. A questionnaire was used as a measuring tool. The results of the study showed that trainees are not satisfied with the reality of the general training, whether in terms of the quality of training programs, the trainers' targets or training authority standards.

Dagher, et al (2016) conducted a study aimed at identifying the degree of compatibility of higher education outputs in Jordan to the labor market needs from the administrators of Jordanian community institutions' point of view. The sample consisted of (380) administrators from local community institutions. The results of the study showed that the estimating of the sample members were average, and the study did not show any statistically significant differences in the degree of compatibility of the Jordanian education outputs to the need of the labor market for all axes and variables of the study. They were represented in the quality of the qualitative level of graduates in Jordanian universities, scientific projects in Jordanian universities, scientific research, conferences and seminars directed to local society, the reputation of Jordanian universities, and the satisfaction of the beneficiary according to the (type of job) variable. The study also reached to several suggestions, including a review of the required educational organization by expanding admission to technical specialties, raising the admission grades in public and private universities, and raising the passing grade in high school to direct students with low grade to vocational education while students with higher grade to technical education. Yunus (2016) performed an evaluation study for the training programs at the Training and Community Service Center at King Saud University from the perspective of the trainees. The study sample consisted of (204)

trainees. A set of proposals and recommendations are presented to achieve its objectives, including Building an effective system to follow up and evaluating the training programs presented to the security sectors in Riyadh, creating a mechanism for making a comprehensive evaluation of those training programs, and paying attention to identifying training need methods.

Similarly, Ziyadat (2016) carried out a study aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of training programs for preparing social studies teachers in Jordan and their relationship to some variables from the trainees' point of view. The study sample consisted of (133) male and female teachers. The results of the study showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of evaluation of the training programs' degree of effectiveness, which is attributed to the variables of academic qualification, number of years of experience, and number of training courses. Issa (2011) illustrated in his study the higher education graduates in Lebanon and their readiness in quantity and quality for the labor market. The findings concluded that there are clear deficiencies in higher education institutions and their professional preparation to meet the needs of the local labor market and the intensity of enrollment in traditional specializations is not corresponding with the needs of the labor market. In a wider range, Al-Obaidi (2009) executed a study on ensuring the quality of higher education outputs in Arab countries and their correlation with the needs of the labor market revealed that the number of Arab universities is increasing significantly, increasing in (2008) by (65.2%) and that most students are enrolled in literary and humanitarian majors. What's more, the outcomes unveiled that most institutions of higher education suffer from weakness in the educational systems and curricula to keep pace with the needs of the global labor market in the Arab countries.

Azzam and Al-Fardi (2009) conducted a study to assess the performance efficiency of private university graduates in banking sciences at Zarqa University, Kingdom of Jordan. The results indicated a lack of suitable competence for working in banking fields, and there are a noticeable gap between Jordanian banks in general and universities. The study recommended the necessity of coordination between departments of banking sciences and defining the efficiency and quality of the banking labor market.

Al-Qanadili (2009) revealed in his study, which was devoted to evaluate the external higher education efficiency for girls and the needs of the labor market in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, showed that higher education for girls did not achieve the ambitions of the Saudi society, as the unemployment rate exceeded 90% in the last six years in this study. The study recommended the necessity of developing the elements of the educational process in order to achieve synchronization between higher education, the student's life needs and the labor market needs.

Sayegh's study (2003) on education and the labor market in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia aimed to lay down a future vision for the year 2020. An imbalance and mismatch are found between educational outputs and the labor market needs. The study recommended the necessity of establishing policies that oblige the educational sector in the Kingdom to conform outputs to the behavioral, scientific, and professional specifications measure up with the needs of the labor market. The findings also clarified the importance of engaging the private sector through increasing the employment of educational outputs, cooperating with educational institutions, and supporting scientific research to eliminate the causes of the low level of employment in the private sector.

Al-Zahrani (2002) conducted a study on the suitability of Saudi higher education for the development and providing national needs of the workforce as well as its economic, social and security implications. The outcomes of the study showed the inability of higher education curricula to achieve compatibility with the requirements of the private sector in terms of employment and technicians. The results also uncovered that the needs of the Saudi labor market are summed up in the medical, health, engineering, technical, industrial, and administrative specializations, information systems, and computers. The findings also elucidated the lack of clear information concerning the labor market needs for various specializations. Hence, the higher education institutions in the Kingdom are not aware of the requirements of economic globalization and the educational challenges resulting from it.

1.1. Commenting on previous studies

It is evident from the previous studies that there is a clear shortage in professional courses, while most studies have shown the existence of a surplus in theoretical disciplines and their need for the labour market in the Arab and Gulf countries (Kuwait University 2016, Public Authority for Applied Education and Training 2003, Al-Zahrani 2002). Most studies have shown a mismatch between higher education outcomes and the needs of the labour market in Arab and Gulf countries (Kuwait University 2010, 2016, Dagher and others 2016, Zahrani 2002, Hariri 2001, jeweler 2003, Issa 2011, Al-Obaidi 2009).

However, some studies have stated that there is no competency in the outputs of higher education and the needs of the actual labour market (Dagher and others 2016, Azzam and Al-Fardi 2009, Al-Obaidi 2009, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry in Riyadh 2005), and some studies indicated the reluctance of graduates to

engage in work in the private sector (Public Authority for Education Applied and Training 2003, Kuwait University 2016, Sayegh 2003, Azzam and Alfradi 2009, Hariri 2001). Studies have shown the inability of higher education institutions to supply the labour market with national competencies to meet actual needs (Al-Hariri 2001, Al-Zahrani 2002, Issa 2011, Saegh 2003).

2. The Problem of the study:

The Public Authority for Applied Education and Training seeks to prepare young cadres in several specializations to meet the labor market needs in the governmental and private sectors. The curricula and programs of the faculties and institutes aim to achieve synchronization between the various specializations and the labor market needs. The lack of compatibility between them created a gap, which led to the existence of many negative results such as an increase in the unemployment rate and a waste of the public money of the state. While many recruiting officials believe that higher education graduates lack the basic practical skills required by the labor market, and the reason for the gap between higher education outputs and job requirements is due from the employers' perspective that the real work environment differs from the theoretical studies they receive. Therefore, the essence of the study problem lies in detecting the graduates of the Authority's suitability from their perspective and the efficiency of the practical and theoretical courses they took in the college to the market needs, to the job satisfaction after they enroll in the work .

.Study questions

This study sought to answer the following questions:

The first question: *What is the level of academic and professional preparation for the Authority graduates to perform the work entrusted to them in their institutions from their perspective?*

The second question: *Are there statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of the academic and professional preparation level of the Authority's graduates to perform the work entrusted to them in their institutions from their perspective, according to these variables (gender, type of sector, field of specialization)?*

3. Objectives of the study:

This study aimed to identify the reality of employing the General Authority of Applied Education graduates who are from various faculties, institutions, and programs for the labor market for the years 2000-2015. Besides, providing job sites for the Authority graduates for the years (2000-2015) in the labor market. Furthermore, the efficiency of their graduates' performance in the years (2000-2015) through the following indicators: the relevance of work to specialization and general competence of graduates through academic and professional preparation in various institutions of the Authority, job satisfaction, readiness to work in the public and private sectors, and the competence of faculty and training staff.

4. Significance of the study:

This study is important because it is in line with the requirements of the supportable development plan in the State of Kuwait (2035) and to take care of the youth and provide job opportunities for graduates in various governmental and private sectors. It is also in agreement with the general objectives of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in caring for its students and fulfilling the labor market needs for technicians, teachers, and technologists. Moreover, the results of this study will help the Decision Support Center and the Programs, and Curricula Center at the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training by introducing or developing the required specializations. Another benefit is that they could either freeze or propose new programs or modern methodology according to the needs of the labor market in planning for the future of the state.

5. Methodology:

This study used the descriptive approach for its suitability for the present study.

7.1 Study tool

The researcher developed a questionnaire as the tool for this study. It was prepared by referring to theoretical literature and previous studies such as the Obaidat and Saada (2010), and Al-Sallal (2013) studies. The questionnaire consisted in its initial form of (45) items, distributed into (10) areas: (self-development, theory courses, general culture, scientific courses, work-relatedness to specialization, the reason for choosing the major, willingness to work, the efficiency of teaching, and training members, job satisfaction, and economic satisfaction.

1.2 Instrument validity

The study Instrument was verified by presenting it to a group of referees from among the faculty members in Kuwaiti universities and some employers. The modifications were made in light of the notes that were given, and the questionnaire consisted of (40) items in its final form.

7.3 Instrument Reliability :

Instrument reliability was verified by applying it to an exploratory sample from the study population, which is not included in the basic study sample, consisting of (30) employers. After two weeks, the questionnaire was re-applied to them, where the correlation coefficient between the two times of application and

stability was calculated in terms of the internal consistency equation Cronbach's Alpha, and table (1) shows these values.

Table (1)
The values of reliability, and internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha

The sequence	dimension	Test-test	(Cronbach's Alpha)
1	Self-development	0.81	0.82
2	Theoretical courses	0.78	0.82
3	General Education	0.80	0.78
4	Practical courses	0.80	0.79
5	Work related to specialization	0.81	0.83
6	The reason for choosing the major	0.81	0.82
7	Readiness to work	0.77	0.82
8	Efficiency of teaching and training staff	0.84	0.82
9	Job Satisfaction	0.81	0.79
10	Economic satisfaction	0.85	0.80
	Average	0.87	0.85

It is noted from the results of Table (1) that the values of reliability and internal consistency by the Cronbach Alpha method were all appropriate for the purposes of the present study.

7.4 Limitations of the study:

This study was limited to a group of Kuwaiti Authority graduates who hold a bachelor's and diploma from various faculties and institutes from the period between (2000-2015) in different work sites in the public and private sectors in the State of Kuwait.

7.5 Population of the study:

The study population consisted of all graduates from all faculties: Faculty of Health Sciences, Faculty of Basic Education, Faculty of Nursing, Faculty of Business Studies, and Faculty of Technological Studies. Also, the institutions of Higher Institute for Communications and Navigation, Institute of Construction, Institute of Tourism and Cosmetology, Institute of Nursing, Higher Energy Institute, Industrial Institute in Sabah Al-Salem, and Industrial Institute in Shuwaikh. In addition to the Institute of Secretarial and Office Management, special training courses in the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training from the years (2000 to 2015) working in the private and the government sectors.

7.6 The study sample

The sample of the study consisted of (6345) male and female students who were selected according to the availability method from the graduates of the Faculties aforementioned above.

7.7 Study tool correction:

To judge the arithmetic means the equation was used) Highest value in ranking - lowest value) /
Number of classes = $(5-1)/3=1.33$
2.33-1 low
2.33 - 3.67 average
3.68 - 5 high

6. Result and Discussions:

8.1 The first question: *What is the level of academic and professional preparation for the Authority graduates to perform the work entrusted to them in their institutions from their perspective?*

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the academic and professional preparation level of the Authority's graduates were extracted to perform the work assigned to them in their institutions, from their perspective, and Table (2) shows that.

Table (2)
The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the academic and professional preparation level for the graduates of the Authority

level	Dimension	arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Item number	level
1	Self-development	3.44	1.18	1	moderate
9	Job Satisfaction	3.34	1.22	2	moderate
10	Economic satisfaction	3.18	1.35	3	moderate
4	Practical courses	3.16	1.38	4	moderate
8	Efficiency of teaching and training staff	3.16	1.31	4	moderate
6	The reason for choosing the major	3.08	1.13	5	moderate
2	Theoretical courses	2.97	1.14	6	moderate
7	Readiness to work	2.95	1.14	7	moderate
5	Work related to specialization	2.87	1.09	8	moderate
3	General knowledge	2.86	1.19	9	moderate
Average		3.10	0.98		moderate

Table (2) shows the level of academic and professional preparation for the Authority graduates' performance at their institutions was average. The arithmetic means reached (3.10) with a standard deviation (0.98) and the arithmetic means of the dimensions came with a moderate degree, ranging between (3.44) and (2.86). This result may be attributed to the faculty members' interest and the authority's management of the outputs and the extent to which it has the requirements of the labor market. These outcomes are an indication that the government should pay more attention to schoolteachers where only qualified teachers should be accepted. In return, this would enhance the quality of students as the base of higher education. The findings are relatively consistent with the study of Kuwait University (2013) while differing from the results of Subagi and Deen (2020) study, which revealed the trainees' dissatisfaction with the reality of general training, whether regarding the quality of training programs or trainers or standards of training agencies.

8.2 The second question: *Are there statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of the academic and professional preparation level of the Authority's graduates to perform the work entrusted to them in their institutions from their perspective, according to these variables (gender, type of sector, field of specialization)?*

In order to answer this question, arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted, the level of academic and professional preparation for the graduates of the Authority with different variables.

8.2.1 First: the gender variable:

Table (3)

Arithmetic means of the academic and professional preparation level of the Authority's graduates to perform the work assigned to them in their institutions from their perspective, according to the students' gender

Dimension	Males	Females	T value	indicator
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	means	deviation	means	deviation		
Self-development	3.01	1.30	3.76	0.99	3.40	0.001
Theoretical courses	2.64	1.23	3.20	1.01	4.02	0.001
General education	2.47	1.25	3.14	1.05	4.00	0.001
Practical courses	2.61	1.51	3.55	1.13	3.98	0.001
Work related to specialization	2.61	1.19	3.05	0.97	3.78	0.001
The reason for choosing the major	2.78	1.25	3.29	0.97	3.98	0.001
Readiness to work	2.67	1.24	3.14	1.02	4.05	0.001
Efficiency of teaching and training staff	2.87	1.39	3.36	1.21	3.87	0.001
Job Satisfaction	2.98	1.34	3.60	1.06	3.90	0.001
Economic satisfaction	2.92	1.43	3.37	1.26	4.01	0.001
Average	3.05	0.97	3.15	0.98	4.06	0.000

The overall findings of Table (3) show that there are statistically significant differences between the average of the level of academic and professional preparation for the graduates of the Authority to perform the work entrusted to them in their institutions, according to the student's gender was statistically in favor of females. It can be noted from the results of Table (3) that the values of "T" for all dimensions were statistically significant, as the significance values were less than (0.05) for each field. It could be attributed to the great need for females to work for several reasons. They want to prove to society that they can be useful just like men. Other reasons might be that they want to achieve their goals, finish their education, and show their self-assertiveness and confidence for the community. As a result, they work hard and efficiently in their companies.

8.2.2 Second: Type of sectors:

Table (4)

Arithmetic means, standard deviations, and a "T" test for independent samples of the academic and professional preparation level for graduates of the Authority to perform the work assigned to them in their institutions from their perspective, according to the type of sectors

Dimension	Government sector		Private sector		T value	indicator
	means	deviation	means	deviation		
Self-development	3.45	1.18	3.38	1.23	1.77	0.076
Theoretical courses	2.98	1.13	2.90	1.18	1.92	0.055
General education	2.87	1.18	2.83	1.22	0.87	0.383
Practical courses	3.18	1.37	3.07	1.45	2.08	0.037
Work related to specialization	2.88	1.08	2.84	1.15	0.80	0.423
The reason for choosing the major	3.09	1.12	3.03	1.16	1.50	0.131
readiness to work	2.95	1.14	2.93	1.18	0.44	0.660
Efficiency of teaching and training staff	3.16	1.31	3.15	1.33	0.20	0.837
Job Satisfaction	3.35	1.22	3.29	1.25	1.38	0.167
Economic satisfaction	3.19	1.34	3.10	1.39	1.83	0.067
Average	3.11	0.98	3.09	1.01	1.03	0.059

The findings of Table (4) revealed there are no statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of the average academic preparation level for graduates of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the different work sector (government / private), except for the number of work courses, where the value of "T" is (2.08). This means that it is statistically significant at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the favor of the government sector. This result might be contributed the reality of employment. The government

has a desire in providing a good living for its citizens. Thus, they may employ not very qualified workers as they can be trained later or even have an experience unlike private sectors they focus on the availability of requirements and skills for the applicant to be accepted. The fact of existing differences between the nature and requirements of work in the government and private sector came along relatively with the result of Dagher, et al.'s (2016) study and Sayegh's study (2003). They encouraged the private sector to employ more students.

8.2.3 Third: Filed of Specialization:

Table (5)

Arithmetic means, standard deviations, and a "T" test for independent samples for the level of academic preparation for graduates of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training from their perspective according to the field of specialization

Dimension	Field of specialization		Not the Field of specialization		T value	indicator
	means	deviation	means	deviation		
Self-development	3.57	1.12	2.91	1.28	5.01	0.001
Theoretical courses	3.06	1.10	2.59	1.21	4.02	0.001
General education	2.97	1.15	2.43	1.23	3.76	0.001
Practical courses	3.33	1.32	2.46	1.41	2.87	0.001
Work related to specialization	2.94	1.05	2.58	1.18	2.86	0.001
The reason for choosing the major	3.17	1.08	2.69	1.23	3.05	0.001
readiness to work	3.03	1.10	2.62	1.35	3.01	0.001
Efficiency of teaching and training staff	3.25	1.28	2.78	1.35	3.10	0.001
Job Satisfaction	3.46	1.18	2.88	1.30	3.88	0.001
Economic satisfaction	3.27	1.32	2.81	1.41	3.78	0.001
Average	3.20	0.86	2.80	0.98	6.04	0.002

It is noticed from the results of the table (5) that there are statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of the average of the academic preparation level for the graduates of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the field of specialization, as the value of "T" was (6.04), which is statistically significant at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$). All the dimensions were of statistical significance in favor of the specialization field. This finding is an interpretation of the fact that the graduates work in their field of specialization in order to employ their acquired skills during the academic years of studying and to increase this knowledge and experience in one major to benefit the labor market. The outcomes are similar to Yunus's (2016) study to emphasize building the students' skills from school level to have highly qualified workers in the future.

7. Conclusion

Preparing qualified graduates is not an easy task where schools, universities, and companies are all responsible to achieve this goal. The outcomes revealed that the level of academic and professional training for graduates was of the normal range. Gender, especially females, played a significant role, as there are statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of an academic and professional preparation level for graduates of faculties. Additionally, the private sector had no statistically significant differences in the government while some practical courses were in favor of the government sector. The field of specialization had a moderate significant statistical difference.

8. Recommendations

In the light of the obtained results, the researcher recommends the following:

- having continuous contact with the labor market, following up on the available job opportunities, and facilitating the process of convergence between job seekers and applicants.
- Educating students and empowering them to move towards non-governmental labor market entities, establish small and medium enterprises, and benefit from the facilities provided by the state such as the National Fund for Small Projects, the Shuwaikh Vocational Incubator, and other facilities provided by the state.
- Establishing vocational guidance and counseling centers in general education schools and providing tests and standards through which students can be directed to various labor market entities.
- Enhancing the ability of graduates to align with the requirements of the labor market by raising the participation of the private sector in the board of trustees in higher and applied education and training

institutions.

- Developing a database system which developed periodically for the labor market sector according to its annual and future needs. Unifying the goals, policies, and visions of public education, higher and professional education institutions that relate to the requirements of the market needs in line with the time change, technological development, and the sustainable development plan of the State of Kuwait.
- Freezing or canceling some specializations in line with the future visions of the sustainable development plan and the market needs.

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